

Exchange Behaviour of Coen_3^{3+} on Soil and Peat Hymatomelanic Acids

U. K. PAL** and S. K. CHAKRAVARTI*

Department of Chemistry, University of North Bengal, P. O. North Bengal University, Darjeeling-784 430

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The exchange pattern of Coen_3^{3+} on soil and peat hymatomelanic acids (SHyA and PHyA) resembles Langmuir type of curves and is dependent on pH; the stronger acidic group, e.g. COOH predominately participating in the interaction at lower pH. The release of Coen^{2+} from Coen^{2+} -acid complexes exhibit that the orders of reactivity for monovalent cations are $\text{H} \gg \text{Cs} > \text{Rb} > \text{K} > \text{Na} \geq \text{Li}$ for Coen_3 -SHyA system and $\text{H} \gg \text{Cs} > \text{Rb} > \text{K} > \text{Na} > \text{Li}$ for Coen_3 -PHyA complex. The release isotherms for bivalent and organic cations indicate the following sequence of reactivity: $\text{Ba} > \text{Sr} \geq \text{Ca} > \text{Mg}$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N} > (\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}$. The reversals of exchangeability for Li and Na as well as for Ca and Sr are noticeable at lower concentration. The exchange isotherms with monovalent cations display that the exchange processes take place in three stages. The thermodynamic equilibrium constants and Gibbs free energy changes for exchange reactions involving bivalent cations have been calculated by using Kielland's equation. The plots of logarithm of corrected selectivity coefficients or thermodynamic equilibrium constants against hydrated ionic radii and the reciprocals of the Debye-Hückel parameter a° , indicate that the relative affinities of the ions for the exchanger substrates are much better correlated with a° rather than with ionic radii.

WHILE the exchange behaviours of some metal ions (chiefly the trace element cations on soil organic matter) have been studied in detail by some workers¹, much less is known about the trivalent metal ions and the least about the complex cations in particular. Moreover, such studies when conducted at high pH, the results are more often than not robbed of exact significance because of the formation of metal hydroxides. Primarily, keeping this limitation in view, in the present investigation the complex inorganic cation Coen_3^{3+} , which unlike Fe^{III} and Al compounds is far less prone to hydrolysis over a long range of pH, has been chosen for interaction with soil and peat hymatomelanic acids. This apart, the published results on similar reactions involving Coen_3^{3+} with clay minerals² as well as with humic³ and fulvic⁴ acids from both soil and peat origins afford a comparison with the present study. Here, an attempt has been made to study the exchange pattern of Coen_3^{3+} on soil and peat hymatomelanic acid systems to have an understanding on the physicochemical aspect of such exchange phenomena in the light of the concepts of Kielland⁵ and Pauley⁶.

Experimental

The alcohol-soluble portions called hymatomelanic acids were obtained from soil humus (Raja Rammohanpur soil in the district of Darjeeling) and peat humus (Fluka, F.A.G.) in the

manner reported in our earlier paper⁸. They were purified in the same way as their humic acid counterparts⁸. The peat and soil hymatomelanic acids are abbreviated as SHyA and PHyA, respectively: SHyA was found to contain C, 54.56; H, 5.51, N, 2.04, ash, 2.2%; and PHyA, 55.78; H, 3.87; N, 0.80, ash, 0.5%.

The study on the exchange behaviour of Coen_3^{3+} on hymatomelanic acids at different pH values as well as at a particular pH (7.5) was following the same experimental procedure as described earlier⁸. To study the exchange isotherms, Coen_3 -hymatomelanic acid complexes were prepared and the exchange reactions were carried out by using different cations including organic ones as reported earlier⁸.

Results and Discussion

The uptake of Coen_3^{3+} by SHyA at different pH values (Fig. 1) increases with increasing pH, because the dissoliation of acidic groups, e.g. COOH and phenolic-OH in the exchanger substrate normally serving as active exchange sites, increases with the rise of pH. The curve shows that there is a limiting pH value at which the exchange processes practically cease. It may be attributed to the fact that at this pH value the dissoliation of the acidic groups in the exchanger phase is too low to permit any significant exchange process to occur. Further, the

*Present address: AD-364 Salt Lake City, Calcutta-700 064.

**Present address: Bhairab Ganguli College, Calcutta-700 056.

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherm of Coen_3^{3+} -SHyA system.

curve suggests two stages of interactions. The first and second stages of Coen_3^{3+} uptake correspond to the pH ranges 2.0-4.0 and 4.0-7.5, respectively, for SHyA and 2.0-4.2 and 4.2-7.5, respectively, for PHyA (not shown). A steady state is reached in each case at pH 7.5. Presumably, at lower pH, the stronger acidic groups take part in the exchange processes while at higher pH all the acidic groups (both strong and weak) get increasingly available for interaction. The exchange pattern of Coen_3^{3+} on SHyA (Fig. 1) and PHyA (not shown) at pH 7.5 resembles Langmuir type of curves. The b.e.c.'s of the acid systems evaluated from these isotherms are 450 and 510 m.e/100 g for SHyA and PHyA, respectively. These values compare well with those obtained by potentiometric titrations with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in presence of 0.5 M BaCl_2 and estimate at 450 and 508 m.e./100 g for SHyA and PHyA, respectively.

The release of Coen_3^{3+} from Coen_3 -SHyA (Fig. 2) and Coen_3 -PHyA (not shown) by monovalent

Fig. 2. Release of Coen_3^{3+} -SHyA complex by monovalent cations.

cations (except H) displays that the exchange processes take place in three stages. At the initial stage the exchangeability is high, then it subsides and again it rises till it tends to reach a steady state in some cases. It is likely that the counter-ions initially replaces Coen_3^{3+} from the weak sites of interaction resulting in high exchangeability. Subsequently, they attack the strongly interacted sites so that the amount exchanged subsides, and finally, the increase in the concentration of the exchanging species makes the process easier to some extent. It may be noted that the reversal of exchangeability is observed for Li and Na for Coen_3 -SHyA system at lower concentration. However, such reversal has not figured with Coen_3 -PHyA complex (not shown) at any concentration. Noticeably, H has exceptionally high exchangeability compared with other counter-ions. The maximum amount of Coen_3^{3+} released by this particular ion is 84% and 95% for Coen_3 -SHyA and Coen_3 -PHyA, respectively. Incidentally, these values are lower with Coen_3 -humic acid systems³ but higher (100%) with Coen_3 -fulvic acid complexes⁴.

The exchange isotherms with bivalent cations and quaternary ammonium ions for Coen_3 -SHyA are shown in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. The corrected selectivity coefficients and distribution

Fig. 3. Release of Coen_3^{3+} from Coen_3 -SHyA complex by bivalent cations.

Fig. 4. Release of Coen_3^{3+} -SHyA by organic cations.

coefficients indicate the following orders of reactivity: for monovalent cations, $\text{H} \gg \text{Cs} > \text{Rb} > \text{K} > \text{Na} \approx \text{Li}$ with Coen_3 -SHyA and $\text{H} \gg \text{Cs} > \text{Rb} >$

K > Na > Li with Coen₃-PHyA complex; for bivalent cations, Ba > Sr ≥ Ca > Mg; and for organic cations, (C₂H₅)₄N > (CH₃)₄N with both the systems. The reversal in the order of exchangeability for Ca and Sr, noted at lower concentration, may not appear very unusual from the consideration of their hydrated ionic radii which are incidentally the same⁷. For monovalent and bivalent cations, the sequence of reactivity, particularly at higher concentration, is in conformity with the lyotropic series. However, for organic cations, though (C₂H₅)₄N⁺ is greater in ionic size than (CH₃)₄N⁺, the former shows greater exchangeability.

The different parameters, like corrected selectivity coefficients (K_c), distribution coefficients (Table 1), thermodynamic equilibrium constants (K) as well as standard Gibbs free energy change (ΔG° = RT ln k) (Table 2) for different exchange

reactions with Coen₃-SHyA and Coen₃-PHyA systems were computed using the earlier methods^{8,4}.

As seen in the Figs. 5 and 6, the curves on the left-hand-side are distinctly nonlinear while those on the right-hand-side are fairly linear. It may be pointed out that the plot of the latter curves is based on Pauley's model which suggests that the electrostatic attraction between the counter-ions and the fixed ionic groups is the significant factor

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS AND CORRECTED SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS FOR DIFFERENT EXCHANGE REACTIONS WITH Coen₃-SHyA AND Coen₃-PHyA SYSTEMS

Electrolyte added	Electrolyte concn (M)	Distribution coefficient	Corrected selectivity coefficient
Coen₃-SHyA system			
LiCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	8.98	9.59 × 10 ⁻³
NaCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	10.25	8.57 × 10 ⁻³
KCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	9.84	9.04 × 10 ⁻³
RbCl	0.60 × 10 ⁻¹	6.48	10.25 × 10 ⁻³
CsCl	0.60 × 10 ⁻¹	4.89	14.24 × 10 ⁻¹
HCl	0.10 × 10 ⁻¹	0.49	9.0 × 10 ⁻¹
MgCl ₂	0.90 × 10 ⁻²	4.09	0.177
CaCl ₂	0.76 × 10 ⁻²	3.42	0.221
SrCl ₂	0.80 × 10 ⁻²	2.78	0.244
BaCl ₂	1.0 × 10 ⁻²	2.93	0.261
(CH ₃) ₄ NCl	0.4 × 10 ⁻¹	8.45	6.77 × 10 ⁻³
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NCl	0.37 × 10 ⁻¹	6.92	9.68 × 10 ⁻³
Coen₃-PHyA system			
LiCl	0.56 × 10 ⁻¹	8.44	8.0 × 10 ⁻³
NaCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	8.44	11.40 × 10 ⁻³
KCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	8.07	12.15 × 10 ⁻³
RbCl	0.60 × 10 ⁻¹	5.74	12.50 × 10 ⁻³
CsCl	0.60 × 10 ⁻¹	5.25	13.80 × 10 ⁻³
HCl	0.40 × 10 ⁻¹	0.52	9.20 × 10 ⁻¹
MgCl ₂	0.90 × 10 ⁻²	5.08	0.157
CaCl ₂	0.76 × 10 ⁻²	3.72	0.212
SrCl ₂	0.80 × 10 ⁻²	3.10	0.236
BaCl ₂	1.00 × 10 ⁻²	2.45	0.260
(OH ₂) ₂ NCl	0.41 × 10 ⁻¹	8.78	9.15 × 10 ⁻³
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NCl	0.37 × 10 ⁻¹	8.44	10.60 × 10 ⁻³

Fig. 5. Correlation between corrected selectivity coefficients (K_c) and (i) hydrated ionic radii and (ii) Debye-Hückel parameter (a⁰) in the exchange of Coen₃³⁺ from Coen₃-SHyA complex by monovalent cations at 0.32 M electrolyte concentration.

Fig. 6. Correlation between thermodynamic equilibrium constants (K) and (i) hydrated ionic radii and (ii) Debye-Hückel parameter (a⁰) in the exchange of Coen₃³⁺ from Coen₃-SHyA complex by bivalent cations.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES EVALUATED FROM KIELLAND'S EQUATION AT 25° FOR THE EXCHANGE REACTIONS WITH Coen₃-SHyA AND Coen₃-PHyA COMPLEX

Exchange system	Thermodynamic equilibrium constant		ΔG° cal mol ⁻¹	
	Coen ₃ -SHyA	Coen ₃ -PHyA	Coen ₃ -SHyA	Coen ₃ -PHyA
K ^{Mg} _{Coen₃}	1.23 × 10 ⁻¹	1.95 × 10 ⁻¹	1248.8	974.4
K ^{Ca} _{Coen₃}	1.74 × 10 ⁻¹	2.19 × 10 ⁻¹	1048.0	905.7
K ^{Sr} _{Coen₃}	1.82 × 10 ⁻¹	2.45 × 10 ⁻¹	1015.5	878.8
K ^{Ba} _{Coen₃}	2.50 × 10 ⁻¹	2.57 × 10 ⁻¹	823.4	809.7

to reckon with in the ion-exchange process. It may be mentioned that the curves relating to the PHyA system have not been displayed because they are similar in feature to those of SHyA system.

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